

The occurrence of two heavy metals, Cadmium and Lead, in the liver and kidneys of Roe Deer at several locations in Central Serbia

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Abstract

Roe Deer is a valued game species for hunting in Serbia. Heavy metals are unwanted pollutants that often occur in environments as a result of human activities. Wildlife inhabits natural environments, where they obtain essential nutrition and water. Therefore, they serve as biomonitors for environmental pollution. In today's world, pollution is unavoidable, but keeping its levels as low as possible is crucial. In this study the roe deer harvested during the regular hunting season by the local hunters were used as biomonitors. Following the harvest, liver and kidney samples from roe deer were collected to analyze lead and cadmium concentrations. The detected heavy metal levels were compared to current legal limits. The maximum permitted concentration (lead and cadmium) in edible offal is 0.5 mg.kg⁻¹, except for cadmium in the kidney, where the permitted concentration is doubled to 1 mg.kg⁻¹. A total of 119 samples were analyzed, including 55 liver and 64 kidney samples, from two locations in Central Serbia. The average concentrations of lead in the liver and kidney for both locations were 0.530 mg.kg⁻¹ and 0.393 mg.kg⁻¹, respectively. The mean concentrations of cadmium in the kidneys were 0.231 mg.kg⁻¹ and 0.491 mg.kg⁻¹, respectively. There were statistically significant differences in the occurrence of lead based on location (location 1: 0,654 mg.kg⁻¹, location 2: 0,378 mg.kg⁻¹); however, the effect of the organ was not statistically significant. A statistically significant difference in lead concentration was observed between locations (location 1: 0.654 mg.kg⁻¹, location 2: 0.378 mg.kg⁻¹). However, organ type did not significantly affect lead levels. The average concentration for the liver and kidney was 0,235 mg.kg⁻¹ and 0,481 mg.kg⁻¹, while locations 1 and 2 were 0,313 mg.kg⁻¹ and 0,394 mg.kg⁻¹ respectively.

Key words: Roe deer, Heavy metals, Cadmium, Lead, Environmental pollution